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ADMIT

Institutional Self-Assessment Tool

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Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the design, implementation, and initial deployment of the ADMIT self-assessment tool for the ethical use of Generative AI in higher education. It describes how the ethical taxonomy developed in D.5.2 was operationalised into a set of indicators, transformed into three role-specific questionnaires, and linked to tailored feedback messages. The document outlines the methodological choices made in formulating items and feedback, the technical realisation of the web-based application, and illustrative use scenarios for students, educators, and institutional leaders. It also highlights how the tool can be embedded into broader institutional strategies for responsible GenAI adoption and briefly points to its current limitations and planned extensions within the ADMIT project.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable presents the development of the ADMIT self-assessment tool on the ethical use of Generative AI in Higher Education. The tool is grounded in the project's ethical taxonomy (D.5.2), which includes eight dimensions and thirty-three measurement items, and is addressed to three main stakeholder groups: students, educators, and institutional leadership. Its aim is to support these stakeholders in reflecting on how GenAI and Large Language Models (LLMs) are used in teaching, learning, and institutional procedures, and to help them identify potential gaps in practices and competences.

The following sections describe how the tool was developed and implemented, and how it can be used in practice. Section 2 outlines the development process, Section 3 presents the online application, and Section 4 discusses limitations and future work. The full list of questionnaire items per stakeholder is provided in Appendix A, while Appendix B includes the prompt templates used for feedback generation.

2. Tool development process

The development of the self-assessment tool followed a two-stage process. In the first stage, questionnaire items were formulated for each stakeholder group, starting from the thirty-three statements of the ethical taxonomy and converting them into role-specific closed-ended questions. In the second stage, feedback texts were designed and generated to interpret users' answers across the eight ethical dimensions and to provide short, targeted self-assessment summaries. An overview of this two-step design is shown in Figure 1.

2.1. Formulation of questionnaire items for each stakeholder

The starting point was the set of thirty-three statements contained in the ethical taxonomy (D.5.2), distributed across eight dimensions. These statements express key concerns about the ethical and responsible use of GenAI in Higher Education but are formulated in an open, generic way. For the purposes of the self-assessment tool, the statements were converted into closed-ended questions that can be answered on a simple response scale and used to trigger different self-assessment scenarios. Since the taxonomy does not distinguish between stakeholder groups, the full set of 33 statements was adapted for the three roles of interest: students, educators, and institutional leadership / administrators.

The transformation from generic statements to role-specific items was supported by the Generative AI system ChatGPT-4.0, which was used to produce role-adapted paraphrases while preserving the underlying ethical meaning and the link to the corresponding dimension. For each taxonomy statement, the model received the original wording together with an indication of the target role (student, educator, or institutional leadership) and was instructed to generate a concise closed-ended question suitable for a self-assessment context.

Figure 1 - Overview of the two-step design of the self-assessment tool.

The resulting formulations were then reviewed and, where necessary, lightly edited by the research team to ensure clarity, consistency of tone across items, and alignment with the overall ethical framework of the project, and were subsequently shared with the other project partners for additional feedback and validation.

An example is shown in **Figure 2**, where the generic measurement indicator “What do we risk losing through the use of AI systems?” is paraphrased into three role-specific closed-ended items for students, educators, and institutional leaders.

For example: What do we risk losing through the use of AI systems? (Taxonomy Measurement Item)

Figure 2. Example of a generic measurement indicator from the taxonomy (“What do we risk losing through the use of AI systems?”)

The final set of questions for each stakeholder group is presented in **Appendix A**, organised by ethical dimension and accompanied by item codes used in the implementation of the tool.

2.2. Design and generation of feedback texts

The second stage of the development process focused on the **feedback** that users receive after completing the questionnaire. The objective is to provide, for each stakeholder and each ethical dimension, a short text that:

- reflects the pattern of answers given to the corresponding items, and
- highlights possible gaps and directions for improvement in relation to the ethical use of GenAI.
- is generated and delivered within the project itself, without relying on any external or third-party service provider, which was an important requirement for all partners.

In order to meet this requirement and to keep the generation of all feedback texts feasible within the timeframe of the deliverable, a simple binary response model (e.g. *agree / disagree*) was adopted. This means that every item answer can be encoded as 1 or 0. For a dimension with n questions, there are 2^n possible answer patterns. Given the numbers of questions per dimension, this leads to 384 distinct answer patterns per stakeholder group, and therefore 1,152 feedback cases in total across the three stakeholders. To handle this complexity, feedback was organised as a feedback database. For each stakeholder group and each ethical dimension:

- all possible answer patterns (combinations of 0 and 1) were enumerated, and
- each pattern was associated with a short feedback paragraph of a few sentences.

Generative AI was again employed to assist in drafting these feedback texts. Using ChatGPT-4.0, the development team provided:

- the list of questionnaire items belonging to a given ethical dimension, and
- a specific pattern of answers for those items (with 1 representing agreement and 0 disagreement).

With carefully designed prompts, the model was instructed to generate feedback that acknowledges areas where the respondent already aligns with recommended practice and focuses particularly on items marked as 0 (disagreement), offering suggestions and pointing to potential risks or missing elements. This process was repeated for the required answer patterns in each dimension and for each stakeholder group, following the workflow summarised in Figure 3.

The resulting feedback texts were collected and stored in separate Excel files for students, educators and institutional actors. During the operation of the tool, users' answers are encoded into patterns per dimension, which are then used to retrieve the corresponding feedback paragraphs from these files. The prompt templates that guided ChatGPT-4.0 in this stage, together with illustrative examples of answer patterns and generated feedback, are documented in Appendix B.

3. The Online Self-Assessment Tool

The questionnaires and feedback profiles described in the previous section are implemented in an online self-assessment tool that can be accessed at:

<https://admit.daissy.eu/>

The application allows users to select their role, complete the corresponding questionnaire, and receive a brief report with feedback for each of the eight ethical dimensions. Institutions may use the tool for individual reflection by students and staff

Figure 3 - Workflow for generating feedback texts with ChatGPT-4.0 and storing them in the feedback database.

or embed it in broader training and awareness-raising activities on the ethical use of GenAI.

When users first arrive at the tool, they encounter a simple landing page that invites them to “Select the role you like and take the self-assessment test!”, with three central buttons for *Student*, *Teacher*, and *Administrator*. This minimalist design helps users immediately understand how to begin and ensures that navigation to the appropriate questionnaire is straightforward (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Landing page and role selection.

After choosing a role, users are taken to the corresponding online form. For example, the student view displays a *Student Form* heading, a short introductory sentence explaining that the section evaluates the student’s experience and perspective regarding the ethical use of GenAI in higher education, and a progress bar indicating how many questions remain. The items are grouped under headings for each ethical dimension, such as *Educational Impact and Integrity*, accompanied by a brief description of the dimension, followed by numbered statements with a binary *Disagree / Agree* response format that reflects the closed-ended structure described in Section 2 (Figure 5).

Student Form

This section evaluates your experience and perspective as a student regarding the ethical use of Generative AI in higher education.

0% Complete 1 of 10

Educational Impact and Integrity

This section examines how GenAI aligns with educational goals, supports student learning, and maintains core academic values.

1. I understand the purpose of using GenAI in my course and how it is meant to support my learning *
 Disagree
 Agree
2. The way GenAI is used in my course helps me learn more effectively. *

Figure 5 - Example page from the student questionnaire.

Once the questionnaire has been completed and submitted, the tool generates a feedback report. In the case of a student, the report contains a section for each ethical dimension (for instance *Educational Impact and Integrity*, *Privacy and Data Governance*, and

Societal, Individual, and Environmental Wellbeing). For every dimension, the title and a short explanatory subtitle are followed by a feedback paragraph in continuous prose that interprets the user's pattern of answers, acknowledges areas of strength, and points to aspects that may require further attention with regard to the ethical use of GenAI (Figure 6).

Feedback

This section evaluates your experience and perspective as a student regarding the ethical use of Generative AI in higher education.

Educational Impact and Integrity

This section examines how GenAI aligns with educational goals, supports student learning, and maintains core academic values.

You show a strong ethical awareness and understanding of how GenAI fits into your course. You trust its use, believe it aligns with learning goals, and see it being handled responsibly and with integrity. You've also thought about what might be lost through AI use, which shows important critical reflection.

However, there are two areas to address. First, you don't feel that GenAI actually enhances your learning, suggesting it may not yet be meaningful or engaging in your study process. Second, the role of GenAI hasn't been clearly communicated, which might be limiting how effectively you can use it.

To strengthen your experience, consider asking for clearer guidance on when and how GenAI should be used in your coursework. Exploring different ways to interact with it—like for brainstorming, feedback, or revision—might also help it better support your learning style.

You demonstrate a clear understanding of how your personal data is managed when using GenAI tools in your courses. It's encouraging that you are both informed about data usage practices and aware of your ability to adjust privacy or data-sharing settings.

This level of awareness is essential for engaging with GenAI in a safe and ethical manner. By staying informed, you're taking an active role in protecting your digital privacy and contributing to a responsible learning environment.

Privacy and Data Governance

This section focuses on the ethical management of data in the use of GenAI systems in education.

Societal, Individual, and Environmental Wellbeing

This section addresses the broader impact of GenAI systems on people and the planet.

Your responses suggest that while you may not see GenAI as offering unique value beyond traditional learning methods, you are clearly aware of the potential negative consequences its use might have on individuals or society. This awareness is a key aspect of ethical digital literacy, especially as AI becomes more integrated into education.

It may be helpful to further explore how GenAI can be meaningfully used to complement—not replace—traditional learning. In doing so, you might discover specific ways it can support or enhance your educational experience while maintaining your critical stance on its broader societal impacts.

Figure 6 - Example feedback report for a student.

4. Limitations and future work

The current version of the self-assessment tool has certain limitations that should be mentioned here. First, since the tool is based on the taxonomy developed in Deliverable 5.2, it is clearly constrained by the fixed set of thirty-three items it includes. Furthermore, the feedback it provides is derived from predefined response templates and is currently at a pilot stage in terms of its use and its ability to offer a clear and comprehensive picture of users' overall perception of GenAI and LLM ethics in higher education. Although the set of questionnaire items is grounded in a solid body of literature and established ethical frameworks, future work is required to test their reliability and, where necessary, refine the questionnaire accordingly. Another direction for extension concerns the translation of the tool into additional languages, as well as the enhancement of feedback so that the suggested actions and solutions are accompanied by references to relevant literature. Finally, as GenAI technologies and regulatory frameworks evolve, periodic updates of both the taxonomy and the tool will be necessary to maintain their relevance.

Acknowledgment

The development of this self-assessment tool was made possible through the collaboration of the ADMIT project partners, who contributed to the review and refinement of the questionnaire items generated with the help of ChatGPT, as well as to the paraphrasing and adaptation of the ethical framework. Generative AI tools were used in a supportive role for drafting, paraphrasing, and editing text; all outputs were critically reviewed and validated by the authors, who retain full responsibility for the final content. Lastly, the diagram in Figure 3, which illustrates the workflow for generating feedback texts with ChatGPT-4.0 and storing them in the feedback database, was created using the online tool Eraser.io.

Appendix A

This appendix presents the measurement indicators (questionnaire items) for the ethical dimensions of generative AI use in higher education, separately for each of the three stakeholder groups: students, educators, and administrators.

A. Questionnaire for Students

1. Educational Impact and Integrity

- I understand the purpose of using GenAI in my course and how it is meant to support my learning.
- The way GenAI is used in my course helps me learn more effectively.
- GenAI is used in a way that supports the goals and structure of the course.
- I feel that the use of GenAI respects core educational values, such as fairness and responsibility.
- I can trust the outputs from GenAI, or I am supported in checking their reliability.
- GenAI tools used in my course respect academic integrity (e.g., no plagiarism, proper citation).
- The role of GenAI in the learning process is clearly explained to me.
- I am aware of the impact of AI when I use it, i.e. critical thinking might be invalidated.

2. Privacy and Data Governance

- I have been informed about how my personal data is used when I interact with GenAI tools in my courses.
- I know whether I can change the privacy or data-sharing settings when using GenAI systems in my learning.

3. Societal, Individual, and Environmental Wellbeing

- I believe that using GenAI in my learning adds unique value that could not be achieved through traditional methods.
- I am aware of the possible negative effects that the use of GenAI may have on individuals or society.

4. Teacher and Student Agency and Oversight

- I feel confident in my own digital and AI literacy skills (e.g., evaluating information, using tools safely, understanding GenAI's limits) to make informed decisions when using GenAI tools.
- I am aware whether my teacher chose to use GenAI in the course or if it was required by the institution.
- If I don't want to use GenAI in a course activity, I can opt out without being penalized or left behind.
- I believe that the GenAI tools used in my learning are accurate and do not mislead me.

- When emotional support or understanding is needed, teachers - not GenAI - are present and available.
- I feel that GenAI supports and enhances my learning experience.

5. Diversity, Non-discrimination, and Fairness

- The GenAI tools used in my courses are equally accessible to all students, regardless of background, location, or individual needs.
- I am aware that GenAI systems may contain biases in the way they were trained, such as cultural or language biases.
- I believe that some groups of students might be unfairly impacted or overlooked by the way GenAI is used in education.
- I trust that my institution or educators are taking steps to detect and address unfair biases in GenAI systems.

6. Accountability

- I know where to go or who to contact if a GenAI tool used in my course does not work properly or causes problems.
- I understand who is responsible for addressing problems or harm caused by the use of GenAI in my learning.
- There is a clear and easy way for me to report concerns or complaints about the use of GenAI in my courses.

7. Transparency

- I have been informed about the kind of data used to train the GenAI tools used in my courses.
- The way the GenAI system works has been explained in a way that I can understand.
- The GenAI system provides clear explanations for its outputs or decisions.
- I understand how the transparency - or lack of it - in GenAI systems affects my learning experience.

8. Technical Robustness and Safety

- I trust that the GenAI systems used in my courses are secure and that my data is protected from breaches or manipulation.
- I am confident that there is a plan in place in case the GenAI system fails or causes problems.
- I believe that the GenAI system I use is regularly checked to ensure it works properly.
- If the GenAI system becomes unavailable, I know how my learning will continue without it.

B. Questionnaire for Educators

1. Educational Impact and Integrity

- I have a clear educational purpose for using GenAI in my teaching and can articulate the problem it helps me address.
- The use of GenAI in my teaching supports and aligns with my pedagogical approach.
- There is evidence that the GenAI system I use supports learning outcomes as intended.
- The effectiveness and educational impact of the GenAI system I use are evaluated, including effects on teaching roles, student well-being, and social interaction.
- I am concerned about the trustworthiness of GenAI and support students in verifying sources used by the system.
- The way I use GenAI in teaching upholds academic integrity, including honesty, fairness, and respect for intellectual property.
- The roles of educators, students, and the institution are clearly defined when GenAI is used in the learning process.
- I have reflected on what aspects of education might be lost through the use of GenAI (e.g., human interaction, critical thinking).

2. Privacy and Data Governance

- I am confident that the way I use GenAI in my teaching complies with GDPR and relevant data protection regulations.
- I can customize the privacy and data settings of the GenAI tools I use to align with institutional or legal requirements.

3. Societal, Individual, and Environmental Wellbeing

- I believe the use of GenAI in my teaching adds unique value to the learning experience that could not be achieved otherwise.
- I am aware of and consider potential negative effects of GenAI on individuals or society when deciding how to use it in education.

4. Teacher and Student Agency and Oversight

- I believe that both I and my students have the necessary digital and AI literacy skills to make informed decisions about using GenAI.
- I am free to decide whether or not to use GenAI in my course/module.
- There is a mechanism in place that allows students to opt out of GenAI-based activities without being disadvantaged.
- I am confident that the GenAI technology I use does not mislead or manipulate students.
- There are procedures in place that allow me to monitor and intervene in GenAI interactions when human empathy or support is needed.
- I believe that the GenAI system I use empowers both me and my students in the learning process.

5. Diversity, Non-discrimination, and Fairness

- The GenAI tools I use are accessible to all students equally, regardless of factors like internet access, infrastructure, or special education needs.
- I am aware of possible biases in the GenAI system's training data, such as cultural, linguistic, or demographic biases.
- I consider how GenAI might negatively affect certain groups of students and take steps to ensure no group is disadvantaged.
- I know whether procedures exist in my institution to detect and respond to bias or inequalities caused by GenAI systems.

6. Accountability

- I am aware of whether a Service Level Agreement (SLA) - a formal agreement specifying support, responsibilities, and how issues are resolved - exists for the GenAI system I use, specifying support, responsibilities, and issue resolution procedures.
- I know who is responsible if the GenAI system causes harm or produces an error that impacts my students or teaching.
- There is a clear and accessible process for reporting issues or submitting complaints related to GenAI tools in my institution.

7. Transparency

- I am aware of the content of the dataset used to train the GenAI system I am using.
- The GenAI system's model is accessible and understandable to me as an educator.
- The GenAI system provides clear justifications for its outputs and decisions.
- The level of transparency in how the GenAI system works supports effective teaching and learning.

8. Technical Robustness and Safety

- I am confident that there are sufficient security measures in place to protect against data breaches or data manipulation in the GenAI system I use.
- I am aware of a contingency plan in case the GenAI system fails or causes an issue.
- I know that the GenAI system I use is regularly checked or updated to ensure it functions correctly.
- If the GenAI system becomes unavailable, I have alternative ways to continue my teaching without disruption.

C. Questionnaire for Administrators

1. Educational Impact and Integrity

- Our institution has clearly defined the purpose for using GenAI in teaching and learning, aligned with specific educational challenges or goals.
- The use of GenAI across our institution supports diverse pedagogical approaches while maintaining educational coherence.
- There is evidence that GenAI is effectively supporting learning outcomes as intended at our institution.
- We have formal processes in place to evaluate the effectiveness and impact of GenAI on learning, including factors such as teacher roles, student well-being, and social dynamics.
- We recognize the risks of using untrustworthy GenAI systems and ensure mechanisms are in place for validating AI outputs and sources.
- Our institution ensures that GenAI systems are used in ways that uphold academic integrity, including honesty, fairness, and respect for intellectual property.
- Roles and responsibilities of educators, students, and administrators are clearly defined regarding the use of GenAI systems.
- We have critically reflected on what aspects of education (e.g. human interaction, critical thinking) may be diminished through GenAI use, and address these risks proactively.

2. Privacy and Data Governance

- Our institution ensures that the use of GenAI in educational settings complies with GDPR and relevant data protection regulations.
- The GenAI tools adopted by our institution allow customization of privacy and data settings to align with institutional and legal requirements.

3. Societal, Individual, and Environmental Wellbeing

- Our institution critically evaluates whether the educational value added by GenAI justifies its financial and environmental cost.
- We assess and consider the potential negative impacts of GenAI use on individuals, society, and democratic values in our decision-making processes.

4. Teacher and Student Agency and Oversight

- Our institution provides adequate training and support to ensure that both teachers and students have the necessary digital and AI literacy to make informed decisions about GenAI use.
- Educators at our institution have the autonomy to choose whether or not to integrate GenAI in their teaching.
- There is a clear mechanism in place that allows students to opt out of GenAI-supported activities without academic disadvantage.

- We assess GenAI systems to ensure they do not mislead or manipulate students in their learning processes.
- Our institution ensures that human oversight is maintained, and that educators can intervene when empathy or human judgment is required.
- GenAI tools implemented by our institution are designed to empower and support both learners and educators in meaningful ways.

5. Diversity, Non-discrimination, and Fairness

- Our institution ensures that GenAI tools used in education are accessible to all students equally, regardless of geographic location, disability, or socioeconomic background.
- We assess GenAI tools for potential biases in their training data, such as cultural, linguistic, or demographic biases..
- We are aware of the risk that GenAI systems may disadvantage certain student groups, and we actively monitor for such impacts.
- There are institutional procedures in place to detect, investigate, and address bias or inequality resulting from the use of GenAI systems.

6. Accountability

- Our institution has a clear Service Level Agreement (SLA) or equivalent framework that defines support, maintenance responsibilities, and procedures for addressing issues related to GenAI systems.
- Responsibilities are clearly assigned at the institutional level for managing and addressing problems that may arise from GenAI use in education.
- There is an accessible and transparent process for educators and students to report concerns, file complaints, or request redress related to GenAI use.

7. Transparency

- Our institution ensures that information about the datasets used to train GenAI systems is available and accessible to staff and stakeholders.
- The GenAI systems we adopt are transparent and inspectable in ways that educators and students can reasonably understand.
- T We prioritize the use of GenAI tools that provide clear and justifiable reasoning behind their outputs and decisions.
- Our institution considers the impact of limited transparency in GenAI systems on the quality of teaching and learning and takes steps to mitigate risks.

8. Technical Robustness and Safety

- Our institution ensures that GenAI systems are protected against data breaches, misuse, and data poisoning, with strong cybersecurity measures in place.
- There is a contingency plan at the institutional level to address failures or incidents involving GenAI systems.

- We conduct or require regular checks to ensure that GenAI systems used in education function correctly and reliably.
- Our institution has procedures in place to ensure continuity in teaching and learning if a GenAI system becomes unavailable.

Appendix B

A. Sequence of Prompts for Customizing ChatGPT Feedback Generation from a Numerical Combination of User Choices

Prompt 1: I want you to create feedback based on the evaluation of the ethical use of a higher education instructor, with respect to the ethical dimension "Educational Impact and Integrity".

There are eight questions—measurement indicators—for this specific dimension: *"I have a clear educational purpose for using GenAI in my teaching and can articulate the problem it helps me address., The use of GenAI in my teaching supports and aligns with my pedagogical approach, There is evidence that the GenAI system I use supports learning outcomes as intended, The effectiveness and educational impact of the GenAI system I use are evaluated, including effects on teaching roles, student well-being, and social interaction, I am concerned about the trustworthiness of GenAI and support students in verifying sources used by the system, The way I use GenAI in teaching upholds academic integrity, including honesty, fairness, and respect for intellectual property, The roles of educators, students, and the institution are clearly defined when GenAI is used in the learning process, I have reflected on what aspects of education might be lost through the use of GenAI (e.g., human interaction, critical thinking)"*.

The instructor can respond with 'disagree' or 'agree.' The feedback will focus on the areas where they answered 'disagree' and need improvement, while for the others there can be a more general comment.

Choose two questions where the instructor responded 'disagree' and provide me with feedback.

Prompt 2: I want the feedback to be shorter in length and structured in paragraphs rather than bullet points.

Feedback Αξιολόγησης: "Educational Impact and Integrity"

Στην αξιολόγηση της ηθικής διάστασης της χρήσης GenAI στην εκπαιδευτική διαδικασία, αναγνωρίζεται η σοβαρή προσπάθειά σας να ευθυγραμμίσετε το εργαλείο με την παιδαγωγική σας προσέγγιση και να διατηρήσετε την ακαδημαϊκή ακεραιότητα. Οι θετικές σας απαντήσεις δείχνουν υπευθυνότητα και επίγνωση των βασικών αρχών που διέπουν τη χρήση της τεχνητής νοημοσύνης στην εκπαίδευση.

Ωστόσο, εντοπίζονται δύο σημεία που χρειάζονται περαιτέρω ενίσχυση. Πρώτον, δηλώσατε ότι δεν υπάρχουν σαφή τεκμήρια πως το GenAI που χρησιμοποιείτε υποστηρίζει τα μαθησιακά αποτελέσματα όπως τα έχετε σχεδιάσει. Η ανάπτυξη μηχανισμών αξιολόγησης της αποτελεσματικότητας του εργαλείου μέσα από συλλογή δεδομένων και ανατροφοδότηση από τους φοιτητές, θα ενίσχυε την αξιοπιστία και τη στοχευμένη χρήση του.

Δεύτερον, η έλλειψη αναστοχασμού σχετικά με τις πιθανές απώλειες στη μαθησιακή εμπειρία, όπως η μείωση της ανθρώπινης αλληλεπίδρασης ή της κριτικής σκέψης, συνιστά έναν κρίσιμο τομέα για περαιτέρω εμβάθυνση. Η συστηματική ανάλυση των συνεπειών από τη χρήση του GenAI μπορεί να βοηθήσει στην υιοθέτηση συμπληρωματικών πρακτικών που διατηρούν την ποιότητα της εκπαίδευσης.

Συνολικά, η πορεία σας προς μια ηθική και αποτελεσματική χρήση της τεχνητής νοημοσύνης στην τριτοβάθμια εκπαίδευση είναι θετική. Εστιάζοντας στις παραπάνω βελτιώσεις, θα μπορούσατε να ενισχύσετε ακόμα περισσότερο τον εκπαιδευτικό σας αντίκτυπο.

Educational Impact and Integrity

The instructor demonstrates a responsible approach in integrating GenAI into their teaching, aligning its use with pedagogical goals and maintaining a commitment to academic integrity. However, there is a lack of clear evidence that the GenAI system supports the intended learning outcomes, suggesting a need for more systematic evaluation practices. Additionally, limited reflection is observed regarding potential educational losses, such as reduced human interaction or diminished critical thinking. Addressing these aspects could enhance both the effectiveness and the ethical deployment of GenAI in the learning process.

Prompt 3: The text will be part of a larger document that discusses eight dimensions separately, each in its own paragraph. So how would it be best to structure the paragraph for this particular dimension?

Prompt 4: You address the user who is responding, and based on their disagree statements, you provide feedback that guides them toward proper use.

Educational Impact and Integrity

In your responses, you show a responsible attitude towards aligning GenAI with your pedagogical approach and maintaining academic integrity. However, you indicated disagreement with two important aspects: providing clear evidence that GenAI supports intended learning outcomes, and reflecting on what educational elements might be compromised through its use, such as human interaction or critical thinking.

To strengthen your practice, it is recommended that you develop systematic ways to evaluate whether GenAI meaningfully contributes to student learning, such as gathering feedback or tracking performance metrics. Additionally, dedicating time to reflect on the broader educational impact of GenAI can help you anticipate and mitigate potential risks, ensuring that essential human and cognitive dimensions of learning are preserved.

Focusing on these areas will further enhance the ethical and effective integration of GenAI into your teaching.

Prompt 5: I have this: "Case EI11. I have a clear educational purpose for using GenAI in my teaching and can articulate the problem it helps me address. EI12. The use of GenAI in my teaching supports and aligns with my pedagogical approach. EI13. There is evidence that the GenAI system I use supports learning outcomes as intended. EI14. The effectiveness and educational impact of the GenAI system I use are evaluated, including effects on teaching roles, student well-being, and social interaction. EI15. I am concerned about the trustworthiness of GenAI and support students in verifying sources used by the system. EI16. The way I use GenAI in teaching upholds academic integrity, including honesty, fairness, and respect for intellectual property. EI17. The roles of educators, students, and the institution are clearly defined when GenAI is used in the learning process. EI18. I have reflected on what aspects of education might be lost through the use of GenAI (e.g., human interaction, critical thinking). Feedback - Educational Impact and Integrity" and for the case "0 0 1 0 0 0 1 " the feedback is "In your responses, you show a responsible attitude towards aligning GenAI with your pedagogical approach and maintaining academic integrity. However, you indicated disagreement with two important aspects: providing clear evidence that GenAI supports intended learning outcomes and reflecting on what educational elements might be compromised through its use, such as human interaction or critical thinking. To strengthen your practice, it is recommended that you develop systematic ways to evaluate whether GenAI meaningfully contributes to student learning, such as gathering feedback or tracking performance metrics. Additionally, dedicating time to reflect on the broader educational impact of GenAI can help you anticipate and mitigate potential risks, ensuring that essential human and cognitive dimensions of learning are preserved. Focusing on these areas will further enhance the ethical and effective integration of GenAI into your teaching. " I will give you other cases so that you can provide me with the feedback.

Prompt 6: 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0

.....
.....
.....

In your responses, you show an encouraging focus on ensuring that the GenAI system you use supports learning outcomes as intended. However, several important areas need further attention. You indicated disagreement with establishing a clear educational purpose for using GenAI, aligning its use with your pedagogical approach, evaluating its educational impact, addressing trustworthiness and source verification, upholding academic integrity, defining roles within the learning process, and reflecting on potential educational losses such as human interaction and critical thinking.

To strengthen your practice, it is recommended that you first articulate a clear rationale for using GenAI in your teaching and ensure it aligns with your overall pedagogical goals. Regular evaluation of its impact on students' learning, well-being, and social interaction is also crucial. Furthermore, fostering students' critical engagement with AI outputs by teaching them to verify information can build trust and responsibility. Upholding academic integrity and clearly defining the roles of all participants in the learning process will safeguard fairness and intellectual honesty. Finally, reflecting on what aspects of education might be diminished through the use of GenAI can help you preserve vital humanistic elements in your teaching.

Addressing these areas will lead to a more ethical, transparent, and impactful integration of GenAI in your educational practice.

Feedback – Educational Impact and Integrity

In your responses, you demonstrate a solid foundation in establishing a clear educational purpose for using GenAI and aligning it with your pedagogical approach, while also ensuring that learning outcomes are supported.

However, several critical areas require attention. You indicated the need to improve the evaluation of the educational impact of GenAI, including its effects on teaching roles, student well-being, and social interaction. It is also important to address concerns about the trustworthiness of GenAI and actively support students in verifying the information provided by the system. Additionally, upholding academic integrity—ensuring honesty, fairness, and respect for intellectual property—is vital for maintaining ethical standards. Furthermore, clarifying the roles of educators, students, and the institution in the context of GenAI use, and reflecting on the possible loss of important educational aspects such as human interaction and critical thinking, will help safeguard the quality and depth of the learning experience.

Strengthening these areas will ensure a more ethical, effective, and student-centered integration of GenAI into your teaching practice.

Prompt n: 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0

Prompt for safety after 10 combinations: I want you to state which choice you understand according to the numbers and then provide me with the feedback.

Example: 1 1 1 0 0 0 1

- EII1: Agree (✓)
- EII2: Agree (✓)
- EII3: Agree (✓)
- EII4: Disagree (⚠ Δεν αξιολογείται η εκπαιδευτική επίδραση)
- EII5: Disagree (⚠ Δεν ανησυχείτε για trustworthiness/verification)
- EII6: Disagree (⚠ Δεν διασφαλίζεται η ακαδημαϊκή ακεραιότητα)
- EII7: Disagree (⚠ Ρόλοι διδασκόντων, φοιτητών, ιδρύματος δεν είναι ξεκάθαροι)
- EII8: Agree (✓)

Εδώ έχουμε **τέσσερα σημεία** που χρειάζονται βελτίωση, αλλά ο εκπαιδευτικός έχει ήδη κάνει **αναστοχασμό** για την απώλεια εκπαιδευτικών στοιχείων, που είναι θετικό!

Να το feedback:

Feedback – Educational Impact and Integrity

In your responses, you demonstrate a clear educational purpose in using GenAI, alignment with your pedagogical approach, and evidence that it supports intended learning outcomes. Additionally, you have reflected thoughtfully on potential educational losses, such as reduced human interaction and critical thinking, which is an important aspect of ethical GenAI integration.

However, there are key areas that require further development. You indicated a need to systematically evaluate the educational impact of GenAI, considering its effects on teaching roles, student well-being, and social interaction. Strengthening your practice also involves fostering students' critical evaluation of GenAI outputs by encouraging verification of sources. Moreover, ensuring that the use of GenAI upholds academic integrity, including honesty, fairness, and respect for intellectual property, is crucial. Finally, clarifying the roles of educators, students, and the institution in the use of GenAI will provide necessary structure and transparency in the learning environment.

Addressing these points will enhance the ethical quality and effectiveness of your GenAI-supported teaching.

0 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 for "EII1. I have a clear educational purpose for using GenAI in my teaching and can articulate the problem it helps me address. EII2. The use of GenAI in my teaching supports and aligns with my pedagogical approach. EII3. There is evidence that the GenAI system I use supports learning outcomes as intended. EII4. The effectiveness and educational impact of the GenAI system I use are evaluated, including effects on teaching roles, student well-being, and social interaction. EII5. I am concerned about the trustworthiness of GenAI and support students in verifying sources used by the system. EII6. The way I use GenAI in teaching upholds academic integrity, including honesty, fairness, and respect for intellectual property. EII7. The roles of educators, students, and the institution are clearly defined when GenAI is used in the learning process. EII8. I have reflected on what aspects of education might be lost through the use of GenAI (e.g., human interaction, critical thinking)."

B. Technical Difficulties During the Process

- The use of computer and browser memory kept increasing as the conversation progressed, making it impossible to generate new information after 67 prompts of this type.
- In the premium version of ChatGPT-4o, after 50 prompts the system requested a waiting period of about three hours before allowing a new submission to this model..

B.1. The need to switch to a new conversation in order to continue the process – Use of new prompts

Prompt 1: i have this: "Case EI1. I have a clear educational purpose for using GenAI in my teaching and can articulate the problem it helps me address. EI2. The use of GenAI in my teaching supports and aligns with my pedagogical approach. EI3. There is evidence that the GenAI system I use supports learning outcomes as intended. EI4. The effectiveness and educational impact of the GenAI system I use are evaluated, including effects on teaching roles, student well-being, and social interaction. EI5. I am concerned about the trustworthiness of GenAI and support students in verifying sources used by the system. EI6. The way I use GenAI in teaching upholds academic integrity, including honesty, fairness, and respect for intellectual property. EI7. The roles of educators, students, and the institution are clearly defined when GenAI is used in the learning process. EI8. I have reflected on what aspects of education might be lost through the use of GenAI (e.g., human interaction, critical thinking). Feedback - Educational Impact and Integrity" and for the case "0 0 1 0 0 0 1 " the feedback is "In your responses, you show a responsible attitude towards aligning GenAI with your pedagogical approach and maintaining academic integrity. However, you indicated disagreement with two important aspects: providing clear evidence that GenAI supports intended learning outcomes, and reflecting on what educational elements might be compromised through its use, such as human interaction or critical thinking. To strengthen your practice, it is recommended that you develop systematic ways to evaluate whether GenAI meaningfully contributes to student learning, such as gathering feedback or tracking performance metrics. Additionally, dedicating time to reflect on the broader educational impact of GenAI can help you anticipate and mitigate potential risks, ensuring that essential human and cognitive dimensions of learning are preserved. Focusing on these areas will further enhance the ethical and effective integration of GenAI into your teaching. ". I will give you other cases for you to provide feedback.

0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0

Based on your responses, your use of GenAI in teaching demonstrates attention to academic integrity, and you show an effort to align its use with your pedagogical approach. However, several foundational areas appear to need further development. Specifically, you have not yet articulated a clear educational purpose for using GenAI, nor provided evidence of its impact on learning outcomes. Additionally, there is a lack of evaluation regarding its broader educational effects, such as its influence on student well-being, teaching roles, or social dynamics.

To enhance your practice, consider clarifying the specific problem GenAI helps you address in your teaching and how it contributes to your instructional goals. Establishing a method to assess its effectiveness — whether through student feedback, performance data, or other metrics — will help validate its educational value. Furthermore, paying attention to aspects such as trustworthiness, role clarity, and potential trade-offs (e.g., diminished human interaction or critical thinking) will support a more ethical and reflective integration of GenAI in your teaching.

B.2. Incorrect interpretation by ChatGPT when the mapping of the user's choice to each question is not restated

Here is the feedback for your case:

- **Case: 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 1**
(Agree with: EII2, EII4, EII6, EII7, EII8
Disagree with: EII1, EII3, EII5)

Feedback – Educational Impact and Integrity:

Your responses reflect a structured and ethically conscious approach to using GenAI. You align it with your pedagogical approach, evaluate its educational impact, uphold academic integrity, define clear roles, and reflect on what may be lost — such as critical thinking or interpersonal connection. These are important aspects of thoughtful and responsible GenAI use.

However, three key areas require attention. First, you have not articulated a **clear educational purpose** or the specific problem GenAI helps you address. Establishing this purpose will bring greater intentionality and coherence to your integration. Second, you report a lack of **evidence that GenAI supports intended learning outcomes**, highlighting the need for data collection — such as performance metrics or student feedback. Third, supporting students in **verifying the trustworthiness** of GenAI outputs is essential to developing digital literacy and critical evaluation skills.

By addressing these areas, your GenAI use will become more purposeful, evidence-based, and pedagogically robust.

B.3. Prompt for revision

The correct is :

"Case: 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 (Agree with: EII2, EII4, EII5, EII7, EII8 Disagree with: EII1, EII3, EII6) "

Feedback – Educational Impact and Integrity:

Your responses show that you are taking a thoughtful and well-structured approach to GenAI use in your teaching. You align it with your pedagogical approach, evaluate its broader educational impact, support students in verifying sources, define roles clearly, and reflect on potential losses such as critical thinking or human interaction. These are strong indicators of responsible and future-aware practice.

However, three areas require attention. First, you have not clearly articulated the **educational purpose** or specific problem that GenAI helps you address. Defining this will bring stronger intentionality and focus to your use. Second, you report a lack of **evidence that GenAI supports intended learning outcomes** — consider gathering student feedback or performance data to assess effectiveness. Lastly, reinforcing **academic integrity** — including fairness, honesty, and respect for intellectual property — is essential to ensure ethical use.

By addressing these areas, your integration of GenAI will become more purposeful, evidence-informed, and ethically grounded.

B.4. To generate feedback for another ethical dimension in a new conversation

Prompt: i have this "Case EII1. I have a clear educational purpose for using GenAI in my teaching and can articulate the problem it helps me address. EII2. The use of GenAI in my teaching supports and aligns with my pedagogical approach. EII3. There is evidence that the GenAI system I use supports learning outcomes as intended. EII4. The effectiveness and educational impact of the GenAI system I use are evaluated, including effects on teaching roles, student well-being, and social interaction. EII5. I am concerned about the trustworthiness of GenAI and support students in verifying sources used by the system. EII6. The way I use GenAI in teaching upholds academic integrity, including honesty, fairness, and respect for intellectual property. EII7. The roles of educators, students, and the institution are clearly defined when GenAI is used in the learning process. EII8. I have reflected on what aspects of education might be lost through the use of GenAI (e.g., human interaction, critical thinking). Feedback - Educational Impact and Integrity" and for the case "0 0 1 0 0 0 1 " gives feedback ""In your responses, you show a responsible attitude towards aligning GenAI with your pedagogical approach and maintaining academic integrity. However, you indicated disagreement with two important aspects: providing clear evidence that GenAI supports intended learning outcomes, and reflecting on what educational elements might be compromised through its use, such as human interaction or critical thinking. To strengthen your practice, it is recommended that you develop systematic ways to evaluate whether GenAI meaningfully contributes to student learning, such as gathering feedback or tracking performance metrics. Additionally, dedicating time to reflect on the broader educational impact of GenAI can help you anticipate and mitigate potential risks, ensuring that essential human and cognitive dimensions of learning are preserved. Focusing on these areas will further enhance the ethical and effective integration of GenAI into your teaching. " I would like you to give me feedback in the case where I have two questions: "PDG1. I am confident that the way I use GenAI in my teaching complies with GDPR and relevant data protection regulations. PDG2. I can customize the privacy and data settings of the GenAI tools I use to align with institutional or legal requirements." These are two questions for the ethical dimension *Privacy and Data Governance*. Please provide the feedback for the combination 1 1, where 0 = disagree and 1 = agree.

Of course! Based on your setup and what you provided, here's a feedback text for the **Privacy and Data Governance** dimension where the answers are 11 (both positive):

Feedback – Privacy and Data Governance

Your responses indicate a strong and proactive stance toward ensuring that your use of GenAI in teaching aligns with GDPR and other relevant data protection regulations. Additionally, your ability to customize privacy and data settings shows a commendable level of control and awareness regarding institutional and legal requirements. This demonstrates a solid commitment to safeguarding student data and upholding ethical standards in digital environments.

To further reinforce this good practice, you might consider engaging in continuous professional development on emerging privacy regulations and ensuring that students are also aware of how their data is managed. Maintaining transparency and involving students in understanding data governance can enhance trust and promote a responsible digital culture in your teaching environment.

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